

Supplementary Material

1 SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND FIGURES

1.1 Figures

Figure S1: Correlation matrix. (A) Pearson correlation coefficient for bioclimatic variables (*bio*), accumulated degree-days over 15 °C from February to October (*ADD*), average minimum temperature in winter (*tmin*), average precipitation during the dry season (*prec*) and solar radiation (*srad*) in Alicante, Spain; (B) Pearson correlation coefficient for bioclimatic variables (*bio*) and accumulated degree-days over 15 °C from April to October (*ADD*) in Lecce, Italy.

Figure S2: Geographical distribution of (●) presence and (●) absence of *Xylella fastidiosa* over climatic covariates in the demarcated area in Alicante, Spain; (A) annual mean temperature ($bio1$), (B) temperature annual range ($bio7$), (C) precipitation of the wettest month ($bio13$), and (D) Purcell's categories based on minimum winter temperature (Anas et al., 2008).

Figure S3: Geographical distribution of (●) presence and (●) absence of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the demarcated area in Alicante, Spain, over the principal components, (A) PC1, (B) PC2 and (C) PC3.

Figure S4: Geographical distribution of (●) presence and (●) absence of *Xylella fastidiosa* over climatic covariates in Lecce, Italy (A) annual mean temperature *bio1*, (B) mean diurnal range *bio2*, (C) mean temperature of the wettest quarter *bio8*, (D) mean temperature of the driest quarter *bio9*, (E) annual precipitation *bio12*, (F) precipitation of the driest month *bio14*, and (G) Purcell's categories based on minimum winter temperature (Anas et al., 2008).

Figure S5: Geographical distribution of (●) presence and (●) absence of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Lecce, Italy, over the principal components (A) PC1, (B) PC2, and (C) PC3.

1.2 Tables

Table S1: Best models for the distribution of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the demarcated area in Alicante, Spain.

	Model ^a	WAIC ^b	LCPO ^c
Models with climatic covariates			
1.	$\beta_0 + v$	617.627	1.638
2.	$\beta_0 + bio7 + v$	617.922	1.650
3.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + v$	618.027	1.639
4.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio13 + v$	620.013	1.653
5.	$\beta_0 + bio13 + v$	620.293	1.641
6.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio7 + v$	620.530	1.636
7.	$\beta_0 + bio7 + bio13 + v$	620.620	1.661
8.	$\beta_0 + PRC + v$	621.386	1.672
9.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio7 + bio13 + v$	622.304	1.641
10.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + PRC + v$	622.520	1.675
Models with principal components (PC)			
1.	$\beta_0 + v$	617.627	1.638
2.	$\beta_0 + PC2 + v$	618.887	1.656
3.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + v$	619.558	1.635
4.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2 + v$	620.005	1.656
5.	$\beta_0 + PRC + v$	621.399	1.672
6.	$\beta_0 + PC2 + PRC + v$	622.634	1.689
7.	$\beta_0 + PC2 + PC3 + v$	623.140	1.599
8.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2 + PC3 + v$	623.171	1.634
9.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC3 + v$	623.364	1.608
10.	$\beta_0 + PC3 + v$	623.530	1.584

^a Intercept (β_0), annual mean temperature (*bio1*), temperature annual range (*bio7*), precipitation of the wettest month (*bio13*), first principal component (*PC1*), second principal component (*PC2*), third principal component (*PC3*), Purcell's risk categories (*PRC*) and spatial effect (*v*).

^b Watanabe Akaike information criterion (WAIC).

^c Logarithmic score of conditional predictive ordinate (LCPO).

Table S2: Principal component analysis (PCA) loadings for climatic variables in the demarcated area in Alicante, Spain, and Lecce, Italy.

Climatic covariates	Alicante			Lecce		
	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC1	PC2	PC3
<i>bio1</i>	0.963	-0.260	0	-0.636	-0.152	0.731
<i>bio2</i>	-0.236	0	0.967	0.955	0	0.138
<i>bio3</i>	0.750	0	0.633	0.923	-0.117	0.160
<i>bio4</i>	-0.926	0	0.347	0.919	0.102	0
<i>bio5</i>	0.888	-0.267	0.343	0.804	0	0.506
<i>bio6</i>	0.947	-0.146	-0.277	-0.964	0	0
<i>bio8</i>	0.934	-0.217	0.107	-0.502	-0.388	0.236
<i>bio9</i>	0.900	-0.388	0.119	0.286	-0.170	0.930
<i>bio10</i>	0.930	-0.320	0.134	0.216	-0.130	0.952
<i>bio11</i>	0.972	-0.202	-0.107	-0.870	-0.147	0.350
<i>bio12</i>	-0.882	0.460	0	0.228	0.922	0
<i>bio13</i>	0.297	0.936	-0.110	0	0.969	0
<i>bio14</i>	-0.937	0.322	0	0.458	-0.782	0
<i>bio15</i>	0.976	0	0	-0.397	0.869	-0.148
<i>bio16</i>	-0.404	0.902	0	0	0.967	-0.16
<i>bio17</i>	-0.967	0.222	0	0.755	-0.327	0
<i>bio18</i>	-0.445	0.836	0	0.796	-0.240	0
<i>bio19</i>	-0.659	0.721	0	0.101	0.959	0
<i>ADD</i>	0.968	-0.228	0	-0.141	-0.121	0.973
<i>tmin</i>	0.949	-0.179	-0.257	-	-	-
<i>precd</i>	-0.925	0.346	0	-	-	-
<i>srad</i>	-0.789	-0.147	0.258	-	-	-
% variability	69.7	18.2	8.5	38.9	28.7	20.1

Table S3: Best models for the distribution of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Lecce, Italy.

	Model ^a	WAIC ^b	LCPO ^c
Models with climatic covariates			
1.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio2 + bio9 + w$	1091.485	0.131
2.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + bio9 + bio12 + w$	1095.184	0.132
3.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + bio12 + w$	1095.307	0.132
4.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio2 + bio8 + bio12 + w$	1095.709	0.132
5.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + bio9 + w$	1095.959	0.132
6.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + bio9 + bio12 + bio14 + w$	1096.218	0.132
7.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + w$	1096.343	0.132
8.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio8 + bio12 + bio14 + w$	1096.348	0.132
9.	$\beta_0 + bio2 + bio12 + w$	1096.362	0.132
10.	$\beta_0 + bio1 + bio2 + bio8 + w$	1096.692	0.132
Models with principal components (PC)			
1.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2 + PC3 + w$	1078.769	0.130
2.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC3 + w$	1079.789	0.130
3.	$\beta_0 + PC2 + PC3 + w$	1080.430	0.130
4.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2 + w$	1081.277	0.130
5.	$\beta_0 + PC3 + w$	1081.607	0.133
6.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + w$	1081.974	0.133
7.	$\beta_0 + PC2 + w$	1082.573	0.133
8.	$\beta_0 + w$	1083.363	0.133
9.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2$	1711.042	0.133
10.	$\beta_0 + PC1 + PC2 + PC3$	1712.478	0.133

^a Intercept (β_0), annual mean temperature (*bio1*), mean diurnal range (*bio2*), mean temperature of the wettest quarter (*bio8*), mean temperature of the driest quarter (*bio9*), annual precipitation (*bio12*), precipitation of the driest month (*bio14*), first principal component (*PC1*), second principal component (*PC2*), third principal component (*PC3*), and spatial effect (*w*).

^b Watanabe Akaike information criterion (WAIC).

^c Logarithmic score of conditional predictive ordinate (LCPO).

REFERENCES

- Anas, O., Harrison, U. J., and Brannen, P. M. (2008). The effect of warming winter temperatures on the severity of Pierce's disease in the Appalachian mountains and Piedmont of the southeastern United States. *Plant Health Progress* 9, 13. doi:10.1094/PHP-2008-0718-01-RS